

A hermeneutical approach to provide robots with socially adaptive perception

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Abstract. Adaptive behaviour is essential for robots to establish natural social interactions with humans, which is grounded and develops from an adaptive perception of the environment and the other agents. At the intersection of social and cognitive robotics, this paper theorises interpretation as a fundamental instrument to provide such skills to robots. First, the hermeneutical circle of context and experience is described as a core element of adaptivity in human perception. Secondly, the process of interpretation/contextualisation is presented through two different but complementary levels. Finally, in a dialogue with the current developments in social robots, the paper brings to the attention some problems or possibilities on the topic.

Keywords. Social Robotics, Adaptability, Personalisation, Shared Perception, Human-Robot Interaction

1. Introduction

Social robotics is an expanding area of research. It is intrinsically interdisciplinary since the interest on the topic is distributed among social sciences, biomedical and robotic engineering, neurosciences, and philosophy and aims to develop and investigate natural interaction between humans and robots [1]. It shares part of the research with other specific areas of robotics, such as cognitive robotics. Cognitive robotics aims at autonomous development, modelling, and porting of cognitive abilities on embodied artificial systems [2]. The present work fits into the intersection between the two domains by reflecting on socially adaptive perception in robots and proposing a theoretical model about it. Adaptive behaviour has already been highlighted for robots as fundamental for establishing a natural social interaction [3,4]. However, adaptive behaviour develops from an adaptive perception of the environment and the other agents. Following this idea, the present research outlines a view of adaptive perception by focusing on two different

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binomials: 1. the circularity between context and experience and 2. the double level of contextualisation.

2. The hermeneutical circle between context and experience

Many theories of perception, even different from each other, have shown the complexity of the human perceptual process and how it grows from the act of experiencing sensations. The theory of Gestalt, for instance, noticed that the single sensation could appear only within a configuration, a complex of structural relations that are primitives to the sensation [5]. Starting from Merleau-Ponty [6], the French phenomenology tradition brought attention to this perceptual process. Richir [7,8] explained how the sensorial configuration of the body ensures the recipience of affections mixed in a vanishing flow of protention and retention that are finally gathered, constituted, and experienced in a more structured and fixed way: as perceptions. Taking a different direction, Helmholtz's concept of 'unconscious inference' recalls the role of experience in shaping perception with the construction of a spatial representation that influences each sensation [9]. Similar ideas inspired other empirical studies on the 'central tendency' phenomenon [10–12], often considered a perceptual mechanism that shows how prior experiences of similar magnitudes influence sensory stimuli. Recently, many models of perception presented the shaping of sensory stimuli as the result of predictions made by the brain based on other information [13]: previous experience, context, expectations, and – in a circularity of perceptual and motor system – motor behaviour [14,15].

Perception is therefore the result of an interpretative process in which each sensation is experienced based on a context and, in turn, contexts inherently shape each sensation. The context allows us to interpret sensations and have experiences, but, on the other hand, it also rises from experiences. It is possible to think about the interdependent relation between sensation and context in parallel with the hermeneutical circle as H.G. Gadamer

Figure 1. The hermeneutical circle between interpretative context and single experiences.

explained it. For Gadamer, the circle between interpreter and tradition reveals the ontological structure of understanding [16]. A pure datum (in our case the *sensation*) never exists for the interpreter (*subjects of the experience*), which is always situated in a tradition (*context*). More thoroughly, the tradition is the pre-condition for each experience made by the interpreter. Still, it is also created by the interpreter, who participates in its evolution inasmuch as they understand.

Taken into our perspective, the repetition of similar events turns into the uniformity of a context that can therefore be known and restricted from experience. In addition, multiple perceptions can be gathered and grasped just because they stand in the background of the same interpretative context [17]. It becomes clear that perception requires both elements: a context to interpret single phenomena (interpretative direction) and the process of learning from experiences to develop a deeper understanding of contexts or the comprehension of novel ones (incremental direction) (see Figure 1). Resulting from this process, the perception may be termed adaptive, as dependent by the present context in which it appears and resulting from a continual process of prediction, evaluation, learning, influence of other experiences, and adjustment to the external reality.

The hermeneutical paradigm may be found meaningful also within the human-robot interaction perspective. We believe, indeed, that it may constitute a valid theoretical model for the development of robots autonomously interacting with humans and, more precisely, for a socially adaptive perception for the following reasons:

- The hermeneutical model well defines the adaptiveness of perception in terms of dependency on context.
- It expresses the continuous evolution of the perceptual process through the twofold, circular direction $\text{context} \Rightarrow \text{experience}$ and $\text{experience} \Rightarrow \text{context}$.
- It has been presented as ontological model of the relation human-world and may therefore be the basis to shape the relation robot-world as well.
- It is able to incorporate the ability to interpret sensorimotor data – one of the elements needed for a cognitive architecture [18] – into the generalization process of context-learning – another core element for robots' autonomy.
- To be correctly and efficiently interpreted, social signals coming from the environment and other agents need a reference to the context and the person, and a constant update to the situation.

Given these considerations, the reference to hermeneutics may truly pave the way to develop a model of adaptive perception for social robots. Additionally, if we consider the growing presence of robots in several social settings and institutions, a model providing robots with such abilities becomes even more necessary. Only a true adaptive perception can indeed make robots reliable partners in social interactions.

3. The two levels of contextualisation

This hermeneutical circle may be seen as a contextualisation process where the interpretative direction is a context-dependent perception, whereas the incremental direction is the characterisation and learning of context, a process that shows how context-awareness, especially in social interactions [19], is never static. Since we deal with *socially* adaptive perception, we also need to remark on at least two distinct architectural levels of contextualisation.

3.1. First level: social contextualisation

The **first level** refers to the social environment. We can label it as **social contextualisation**. The environment connected to social contextualisation can be seen as the background social context for the perceiver. In turn, this architectural level is structured in non-hierarchical but descriptive subcategories, each defining specific social properties of the situation where the perceiver is immersed (see Figure 2). This background should function as a hermeneutical context for the adaptive perception of the robot to interpret similar information as different depending on the situation. Hence, the information gathered from sensors about subjects and objects in the environment (velocity, acceleration, facial expressions, sound volume, voice tones, etc.) needs to be immediately contextualised based on the social situation. Following the interpretative direction of the circle, the social context should shape, structure, and gather the single experiences, thus allowing the adaptivity of the robot's perception and, accordingly, its behaviour. In this perspective, every experience should concur in the constitution of a structure of contexts, open to a continual learning process, and used, in turn, to interpret novel experiences and enhance the adaptivity of perception. Robotics research has worked to endow robots with context-dependent perceptual abilities. Nigam and Riek [20] trained a network with multimodal and unimodal information coming from real-world scenarios to classify situational contexts and enhance robots' perceptual abilities. Moreover, Zaraki et al. [21] developed a Social Perception System that also interprets and stores high-level features of people and the environment with an awareness of the real-world contents. A top-down controller in which the attentional inputs are influenced and processed through information about the environmental and social contexts has also been proposed by Lanillos et al. [22].

3.2. Second level: personalisation

The **second architectural level** (see Figure 2) deals with each specific agent with whom the robot interacts. At this level, the robot's perceptions are socially interpreted based on users' qualities, attributes, and previous experiences with the robot. The contextualisation becomes therefore **personalisation**: the robot perceives the world around based on the other agents, which comes to be the context to interpret the world. More specifically, in the case of repeated interactions, the robot would use the

Figure 2. The two architectural levels of contextualization for a socially adaptive perception in robots

characteristic of the agents, their usual behaviour and expressions (known, in turn, from features like voice tone and volume, movements velocity, proxemic, etc.), and those personal preferences that have been learned through prior experience (inclination to sociality, specific verbal or body language, habits, and routines, etc.) both to understand the environment and the behaviour of the agent. On the other hand, following the incremental direction of the hermeneutical circle, each interaction would improve the agents' characterisation and make them the context of future interpretations. The importance of personalisation has been considered in social robotics research. In particular, several studies reveal that personalisation positively affects user attention and engagement [23,24]. Moreover, different personalised learning models have been developed based on user personality traits [25] and affective behaviour [23,26].

4. Examples of double-level contextualisation for HRI in social institutions

As long as robots are starting to have a role in people's (might they be customers, citizens, or users) experience of social institutions, it becomes always more evident they need the ability to adapt to several scenarios in which they are involved. In this perspective, two examples might make more explicit the benefit of a model that considers concurrently the double level of contextualisation we explained above.

4.1. Nursing home

Nursing homes are one the primary settings that social robots are expected to populate consistently with the twofold role of assistive and companion robots [27]. It is also one of the social environments that long-term personalisation studies have addressed more frequently in the field of HRI [28]. Reducing elderly people's stress, taking simple health parameters, doing brain-training exercises, or entertaining them are only some of the tasks social robots might tackle.

Interestingly, a case study in a nursing home evidenced that elderly people conceived the robot's adaptiveness to the user's needs and to the context as essential for its usefulness and acceptance [29]. Following this direction, a personalised perception of each patient's behaviour should be based on their medical history, cognitive abilities, personality, social attitude, and even positive or negative attitudes toward the robot. On the other hand, also adaptation to the social context is important. To do this, we advocate that robots need to primarily create a referential context to better interpret the information of the specific environment where it is engaged. The same environment can indeed be defined by several social contexts. In a nursing home, the robot might face different social groups, patients, medical and paramedical staff, and visitors. Moreover, the robot might find people from these three groups together or separately. Patients' bedrooms are a different, more private, and calmer social environment than common rooms, or central halls. A model helping robots understand such differences, create interpretative contexts, and use these social contexts to perceive people and coherently interact with them would profoundly enhance their social intelligence.

4.2. Schools

In the last years, many studies have been assessing the effects of social HRI on children learning, suggesting that interactive robots might positively influence educational

contexts [4]. If so, the employment of robots as tools for teaching in dyadic or multi-party interactions might noticeably increase in the near future, especially considering the different educational needs children in the same classroom usually have.

Personalisation appears, therefore, fundamental for a genuinely positive interaction with single children. For instance, in the case of robots used as learning companions, the benefit of personalised interaction and robot adaptiveness proved beneficial to child learning [30]. But it is worth considering the different behaviours the robot should engage in front of a single child, several children, the teacher, or the entire classroom and, going backward in the robot's decision-making process, how it interprets sensory signals. Volume voice, bodily poses, and motion, and gaze information might be markers of humans' attention, internal state, engagement, turn-taking dynamics, and social roles, which should be attentively considered when dealing with class dynamics or learning cognitive processes. The presence of one or more children, the entire class with the teacher, or the teacher alone, are all different school scenarios that demand a socially adaptive perception to the robot. That is the social contextualisation level of perception that has been described above. Yet, it is self-evident how this should be considered as intersected to personalisation to the single user or group of users.

5. Further considerations for implementing a model of socially adaptive perception

The distinction and definition of these two levels, together with the implied hermeneutical circle, bring some considerations.

First, the two levels of contextualisation are not antithetical but complementary and integrative. Although they are usually investigated separately, they should be thought of together. Churamani et al. [28] propose an attractive incremental learning model where both the adaptivity toward a context and the personalisation to single users are considered. This research includes learning context-specific behaviour and personalised affective perception and is, therefore, an interesting model that starts combining the user-specific attributes with the general context. However, the integration of the two levels is still not entirely reached. The same person behaves indeed diversely in different social environments. Thus, in the eyes of the robot, each user's behaviour should be perceived not only according to the user's personality but also to the social environment in which it occurs. On the other hand, the robot should also interpret the social environment based on information from the people who populate it. Their behaviour or affective expression may give essential cues to understand the social context. Concerning the incremental direction of the hermeneutical circle, the definition of contexts of both levels (social environments and single users) is strengthened by this integration so that the information coming from each of the two levels allows to deepen the learning in the other level.

A second point is critical to consider that such modelling may positively and negatively affect the robot's behaviour. As a positive consequence, the use of a socially adaptive perception model, based on the circle context-experience and structured in the two different levels, could help the robot's incremental learning process and ensure at the same time a generalisation and a characterisation of the acquired knowledge. The use of general contexts of perception, operating with interpretative rules such as early-clustering of the data with respect to prior contexts through integration or exclusion mechanisms, may also reduce the variability of what is perceived and, therefore, the problems connected to the high dimensionality of incremental databases, such as real-

time response to online learning and catastrophic forgetting [31]. Conversely, it may also cause errors and perceptual biases as adverse effects. A too strong influence of a context or a too strong weight given to previous experience may misrepresent the real significance of an event. Moreover, the generalisation process may bring wrong predispositions and distortions from reality, a problem that occurs in the case of unbalanced learning. That is why it becomes crucial to find a reasonable equilibrium between the influence of the interpretative and predictive models and, on the other hand, the control and correction of the generalisation procedures.

A third element refers to the interactive feature of the second level of interpretation. Indeed, the agents to whom the robot adapts its perception are not representable as static context to learn. Personalisation would always be in progress and amended because every agent would constantly change habits, preferences, and behaviour, depending on the context and over time. Moreover, it is crucial to consider that the robot is not neutral in the interaction. Its verbal and non-verbal behaviour may, in turn, affect the user's behaviour. Therefore, the two partners, the human user and the robotic agent, are not static entities and influence each other during the interaction in a reciprocal and continual exchange and adaptation [32].

A final factor presents the socially adaptive perception as an essential means to reach an effective human-robot interaction. The core aspect is that the agents perceived by the robot are other subjects of experience, each with their perspective on the environment. For this reason, the robot needs to consider these points of view. Specifically, the users' perspective on the environment may be inferred through their non-verbal, para-verbal, and verbal communication and behaviours and give the robot, through an intersubjective and triangulated perception [33], an augmented understanding of the environment. We can call this phenomenon 'Shared Perception', describing how co-present subjects in the same environment may affect, modify, and even enhance others' perception [34]. And if we think about robotics, 'Shared Perception' may lead to a double benefit. The robot may compare the other's perspective with its perception, which may bring an increasingly common ground for the interaction. Regarding the hermeneutical circle, the Shared Perception may produce a deeper understanding of the social environment that, in turn, can be used later to interpret novel experiences and enhance the social adaptivity of the robot.

In conclusion, to develop social skills in robots, we advocate that it is essential to start with an adaptive model of perception that allows robots to interpret the world starting from the social environment and the single users. To this aim, it might be crucial to consider the idea of a hermeneutical architecture of social contexts based on the two abovementioned levels. On the one hand, such architecture should be open-ended and enhanced by the robot's novel experiences; on the other hand, it should be used to interpret the same incoming experiences and help the robot represent the social world.

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